

SIMULATION OF FLEXURE IN OFF-AXIS THREE-POINT BENDING TEST BY A FINITE-ELEMENT CODE

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SUMMARY: The present paper is devoted to an application of a hierarchical model of unidirectional composite [1] to the finite element calculation of the three-point bending test in the quasi-static statement for a fibrous unidirectional composite. The finite element method (FEM) in use is based on the Hellinger-Reissner variational principle with assumed stress and displacement fields. Internal (structural) variables are calculated by the time increments where time is a load parameter. The arrangement of fibres and the component's debonding are not considered in the model. However, employing the structural parameters, the chances of the debonding between the constituents can be estimated. Numerical results confirm the conclusion of the beam theory that at the symmetrical loadings (the fibre direction is coincident with the load axis) and low span-to-depth ratio the shear failure prevails. At the same time, in the range of low span-to-depth ratios the influence of the fibre orientation is essential and provokes the mixed mode of fracture at the off-axis loading. Large span-to-depth ratio induces tensile fracture. However, again the off-axis loading destroys clearly defined boundaries of localised deformation and induces the peculiarities typical for the mixed mode of failure.

KEYWORDS: hierarchical model, homogenization approach, finite-element computation, three-point bending test, off-axis loading, fibrous unidirectional composite.

INTRODUCTION

The three-point bending test is one of the very popular tools for the study of the strength properties of material. The wide use of the method for composites faces peculiar features due to the non-isotropic and microstructural behaviour of composite beam, especially under the conditions of the off-axis loading. The complex stress state in the beam was understood for a long time. However, due to the convenience and availability of the test for mechanical assessment of the material properties, simple solutions of the beam theory [2] are widely used for acquisition of the shear and tensile stresses at failure in the three-point bending test.

In the case of the off-axis loading of composites the sample orientation is an essential parameter of the test. It is extremely important in this situation to understand which of the parameters, including the sample orientation and the span-to-depth ratio, are related to mechanical properties of the material and which ones are associated with the problem statement. Mathematical simulation is an invaluable tool in this situation.

The present paper is devoted to the numerical simulation of the problem in the quasi-static plane statement. A hierarchical model of unidirectional composite developed earlier [1,3] is

used for the development of a finite-element program and for numerical simulation. The Onzager principle is valid for the model and it enables us to construct the FEM algorithm with symmetrical stiffness matrix.

Numerical results for the graphite-epoxy composite at the variety of the off-axis angles (the angle between fibre and the load axis) and the span-to-depth ratios are compared with the experiment [4] in the critical load at failure. It is shown that the transition from the shear to the flexure depends not only on the span-to-depth ratio but on the off-axis angle as well.

MODEL OF THE COMPOSITE

The system of the constitutive equations of the model [1,3] contains evolutionary relations for a rotation tensor determining the fibre orientation, a tensor of structural parameters Δ , which is responsible for the internal microstresses along fibres, and equations for elastic deformations (the tensor of elastic distortions a_{ij}). In the two-dimensional case the equations take the form:

$$\frac{da_{ij}}{dt} + a_{ik} \frac{\partial v_k}{\partial x_j} = -a_{ik} \psi_{kj}, \quad \frac{d\tilde{\Delta}}{dt} = -\tilde{\lambda}, \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{d\varphi}{dt} = \frac{a_{21}a_{22}(\psi_{11} - \psi_{22}) + (a_{22}^2 - a_{21}^2)\psi_{12}}{a_{11}a_{22} - a_{12}a_{21}},$$

here fibres lie in the (x_1, x_2) - plane, φ is the angle between fibre and the x_1 - axis in the unloaded state, the tensor of structural parameters reduces to a sole parameter $\tilde{\Delta}$ - the difference between elastic strains in the constituents, which determines the internal stresses along the fibre, v_i - components of the velocity vector. Variables under tilde are associated with the local coordinate system connected with fibre. The tensor of elastic distortion A with components a_{ij} is linked with the standard tensor of elastic deformations ε^e by the rule: $\varepsilon^e = (I - A^T A) / 2$, the superscript T denotes transposition. Combination of a_{ij} resulting in ε^e gives the following approximation of the constitutive equation for ε^e in the rectangular coordinate system associated with fibre:

$$\frac{d\varepsilon_{ij}^e}{dt} = \frac{d\varepsilon_{ij}}{dt} - \psi_{ij}, \quad (2)$$

here the rate of total deformation in the right side results from the components of the strain rate tensor $\partial v_i / \partial x_j$, ψ_{ij} are combinations of the state functions of constituents, which are responsible for the irreversible (plastic) deformation of composite and will be detailed later. Internal potential is expressed (for the isoentropic case) by the formula derived in details with the help of homogenization procedure in [3]: $E = (\sigma_{ij} \varepsilon_{ij}^e + \tilde{q} \tilde{\Delta}) / 2$, here $\tilde{q} = E_{\tilde{\Delta}}$. In the coordinate system associated with fibre the stress tensor σ is related to the elastic strain ε^e by the Hooke's law:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{11} &= C_{11} \epsilon_{11}^e + C_{12} \epsilon_{22}^e + C_{12} \epsilon_{33}^e, & \sigma_{22} &= C_{12} \epsilon_{11}^e + C_{22} \epsilon_{22}^e + C_{23} \epsilon_{33}^e, \\ \sigma_{33} &= C_{12} \epsilon_{11}^e + C_{23} \epsilon_{22}^e + C_{22} \epsilon_{33}^e, & \sigma_{12} &= C_{66} \epsilon_{12}^e. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Effective elastic moduli C_{ij} result from the elastic moduli of composite constituents according to the homogenization procedure described in [1,3]. Differential consequences of the conservation laws are the governing equations of the model (the momentum and energy equations) for the fibrous composite and they have the standard form.

We reduce the model to the quasi-static case by the following simplifications. Firstly we consider t as a loading parameter similar to the loading parameter in the incremental theories of plasticity. The linkage of the load with t can be established from the given rate of loading \dot{p} . The given loading is reached in 'time' by increments proportional to a step Δt . The inertial terms and the time derivative terms in the momentum equation are dropped.

We restrict ourselves by the isoentropic approximation. Therefore, the standard equations of equilibrium are valid. The stress-strain relations are obtained from the Hooke's law (3) and the 'kinetic' laws (2) relating the elastic strain to the total deformation.

DESCRIPTION OF THE ALGORITHM

We consider the 2D-statement in the (x_1, x_2) - plane, where fibres are lying in the plane and $\varphi(x_1, x_2)$ is the angle between fibre and x_1 . In the paper we assume the plane strain state, that is $\epsilon_{33} = 0$, where ϵ - the tensor of total strain.

A method of study employed in the paper is two-dimensional finite element analysis based on a mixed stress-displacement formulation through the Hellinger-Reissner variational principle [5]. The formulation uses the four-node isoparametric quadrilateral element with assumed stress σ and displacement u linear distributions over the element.

The basic problem for the method design is the construction of the stress-strain linkage that can be expressed in increments by the general formula:

$$\Delta \sigma' = D \Delta \epsilon' + G, \quad (4)$$

here σ' and ϵ' are 3-pseudovectors with components $\sigma_{11}, \sigma_{22}, \sigma_{12}$, etc. When the relation (4) is derived, the finite element theory for the Hellinger-Reissner principle gives the standard system of linear equations [5]:

$$H \bar{\sigma} + R \bar{u} = M, \quad R^T \bar{\sigma} = L, \quad (5)$$

here $\bar{\sigma}$ and \bar{u} are assumed stresses and displacements for the given increment, H, R, M, L are assembled matrices. If D in (4) is a symmetrical matrix, then H in (5) is symmetrical along with the corresponding stiffness matrix $K = R^T H^{-1} R$. This fact is extremely important for the design of efficient and economic FEM algorithm.

In order to derive (4) we use constitutive equations of the model (1)-(3). Let us note that the first term in the equation for elastic strain is easily found from both the given displacements (they are connected with velocities by obvious formula $u = v \Delta t$) and coordinates. The second term is responsible for the inelastic behaviour of constituents and, as a consequence, of the composite. In the coordinate system related to fibre it takes the form [3]:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{\psi}_{11} &= \alpha_{11} \tilde{\sigma}_{11} + \alpha_{12} \tilde{\sigma}_{22} + \alpha_{13} \tilde{\sigma}_{33} + \beta_1 \tilde{q}, \\
 \tilde{\psi}_{22} &= \alpha_{12} \tilde{\sigma}_{11} + \alpha_{22} \tilde{\sigma}_{22} + \alpha_{23} \tilde{\sigma}_{33} + \beta_2 \tilde{q}, \\
 \tilde{\psi}_{33} &= \alpha_{13} \tilde{\sigma}_{11} + \alpha_{23} \tilde{\sigma}_{22} + \alpha_{33} \tilde{\sigma}_{33} + \beta_3 \tilde{q}, \\
 \tilde{\psi}_{12} &= \alpha_{66} \sigma_{12}, \quad \tilde{\lambda} = \beta_1 \sigma_{11} + \beta_2 \sigma_{22} + \beta_3 \sigma_{33} + \gamma \tilde{q},
 \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

The symmetry properties of the coefficients $\alpha_{ij}, \beta_i, \gamma$ in (6) follow from the Onzager principle proved for the model in [3]. Here $\tilde{q} = E_{\tilde{\lambda}}$, the coefficients in (6) are combinations of functions written out in [3] which describe the inelastic behaviour of constituents.

The initial step is the calculation of the rotation matrix B from the angle φ obtained on the previous increment step. The matrix connects a tensor F in the Cartesian system and that in the local coordinate system associated with fibre by the transformation rule:

$$\tilde{F} = B^T F B, \quad B = \begin{pmatrix} \cos(\varphi) & \sin(\varphi) \\ -\sin(\varphi) & \cos(\varphi) \end{pmatrix}. \tag{7}$$

The system of constitutive equations (1) is used in increments, with the given time step Δt , which may be changed subject to the stability condition:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Delta a_{ij} &= -a_{ik} \frac{\partial \Delta u_k}{\partial x_j} - a_{ik} \psi_{kj} \Delta t, \\
 \Delta \varphi &= \omega \Delta t, \\
 \Delta \tilde{\Delta} &= -\tilde{\lambda} \Delta t,
 \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

here ω is the right-hand side in the third equation of the system (1).

Because the microstrains and, as a consequence, $\tilde{\Delta}$ are associated with internal processes in the composite so we consider this parameter separately from the set of the strain variables. It should be noted that from the point of view of the mathematical statement the variables σ and q , as well as ε and Δ are equivalent and they may be involved in the variational principle on the same rights. This becomes essential for the dynamic problem. In the present case we calculate ε and $\tilde{\Delta}$ separately.

For a given step equation (6) is written in increments as the following (in the matrix form):

$$\Delta \Psi = F \Delta \sigma + \Psi^0 , \quad (9)$$

F is composed of the coefficients of (6), Ψ^0 is a value of the Ψ -dependence on the previous incremental step. From the Onzager principle F is a symmetrical matrix. The constitutive equation (2) for ε^e in the local system associated with fibre gives

$$\Delta \varepsilon^e = \Delta \varepsilon - \Delta \Psi .$$

Then the Hooke's law (3) is rewritten as

$$\Delta \sigma = C \Delta \varepsilon^e = C (\Delta \varepsilon - \Delta \Psi) .$$

Invoking (9), we have

$$C \Delta \varepsilon = (I + C F) \Delta \sigma + C \Psi^0 \quad \text{or} \quad \Delta \varepsilon = (C^{-1} + F) \Delta \sigma + C \Psi^0 . \quad (10)$$

Multiplying (10) on B from the left and on B^T from the right, we have one of the forms of (4).

It should be noted that due to both the symmetry of C (it means the material symmetry of the transversally isotropic material) and the symmetry of F (it means the fulfillment of the Onzager principle) we have the symmetry of D in (4).

Thus, the finite element algorithm can be designed with the symmetrical matrix H in the basic system of linear equations (5) and, as a consequence, with the symmetrical stiffness matrix. It can be straightforward verified that the condition of the plane strain state $\varepsilon_{33} = 0$ leads to modifications of matrices C and F in (10) in such manner that their symmetry survives.

MATHEMATICAL STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The three-point bending problem is approximated by the plane bending of the plate initially located in the following region of the space:

$$-S/2 < x_1 < S/2 , \quad -h < x_2 < 0 , \quad -\infty < x_3 < \infty .$$

Hereafter, we will refer to the crosssection $x_3 = 0$ of the plate. "Ends" ($x_1 = \pm S/2$) of the plate are clamped, i.e. $u = 0$ at $x_1 = \pm S/2, -h < x_2 < 0$.

The rest of the plate's boundary (except for the point of application of load) is free of normal stresses: $\sigma_{nn} = \sigma_{n\tau} = 0$, where n, τ are the normal and tangent vectors to the boundary. At the point of loading (initially $x_1 = x_2 = 0$) a constant rate of the load is applied:

$$u_n = \dot{\varepsilon}_0 \cdot t , \quad (11)$$

t is a parameter of loading (time), $\dot{\epsilon}_0$ is a given constant.

In the model, the composite elastic properties are determined by the properties of constituents: graphite fibres and epoxy matrix are assumed to have the following Young's moduli E_f, E_m , the shear moduli G_f, G_m and the Poisson's ratio ν_f, ν_m :

$$E_f = 300\text{GPa}, G_f = 125\text{GPa}, \nu_f = 0.2, E_m = 6.56\text{GPa}, G_m = 2.52\text{GPa}, \nu_m = 0.3.$$

The fracture properties of the constituents are expressed in the work by the stress limit. In the viscoelastic model the number of constants in a relevant dependence must correspond to the number of experimental points. As a dependence responsible for inelastic behaviour we choose the two-constant "thermal activation" function of the relaxation time τ_T on the shear stress in the following form: $\tau_T = \exp(U_0 - \gamma_0 \mathcal{J})$, here U_0, γ_0 are the material constants of constituents, the invariant of the stress tensor \mathcal{J} :

$$\mathcal{J} = \left[(\sigma_{11} - \sigma_{22})^2 + (\sigma_{11} - \sigma_{22})^2 + (\sigma_{11} - \sigma_{22})^2 + 6\sigma_{12}^2 \right]^{1/2}.$$

In order to construct this two-constant dependence for each constituent we must give two stress limits (σ_f^1, σ_f^2 for fibres and σ_m^1, σ_m^2 for matrix) at two strain rates ($\dot{\epsilon}_1, \dot{\epsilon}_2$). A method of the construction of the τ_T -dependence with the use of these data is described in [6]. As an example, the following data has been selected:

$$\sigma_f^1 = 2.3\text{GPa} \text{ at } \dot{\epsilon}_1 = 1\text{m in}^{-1}, \sigma_f^2 = 2.1\text{GPa} \text{ at } \dot{\epsilon}_2 = 0.01\text{m in}^{-1},$$

$$\sigma_m^1 = 0.13\text{GPa} \text{ at } \dot{\epsilon}_1 = 1\text{m in}^{-1}, \sigma_m^2 = 0.1\text{GPa} \text{ at } \dot{\epsilon}_2 = 0.01\text{m in}^{-1},$$

ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

On calculations the rate of loading in (11) has been chosen in accordance with the experiment [4] $\dot{\epsilon}_0 = 0.1\text{m in}^{-1}$ at $h = 5\text{mm}$, the fibre content $c = 0.538$.

Our primary attention will be paid to the fulfilment of failure criterion. As the criterion we take the approaching of the stress limit. In the figures we draw the cross-section of the beam with dashed zones. They correspond to an excess in the stress limit for composite. Simultaneously we analyse the following parameters: the tensile stress along the plate surface (initially σ_{11}), the fibre stress in the coordinate system associated with fibre, the internal parameter $\tilde{\Delta}$ along the fibre, which is responsible for microstress (internal microstress may be the cause of debonding).

We approximate the constituents by isotropic materials so we restrict ourselves at the microstructural consideration by the stress along the fibres, although the graphite fibres may possess strong anisotropic properties. The limit in $\tilde{\Delta}$ can be assessed from the following reason: invoking the interlaminar shear stress for the composite [4] 0.06GPa as a basic point

for \tilde{q} (see description of the model) we can find a critical value of $\tilde{\Delta}$ for the given constituents $\tilde{\Delta} \approx 0.02$. Keeping in mind that the debonding may be caused either the deformation of fibre or matrix this value can vary up to five times (according to the ratio of the Young's modulus of fibre to the matrix's one).

Fig. 1: The reduced load versus the span-to-depth ratio at the variety of the off-axis angles (curve 1- 0 deg , 2 - 15 deg , 3 - 30 deg , 4 - 45 deg), points are the corresponding experiment [4].

The simple beam theory [2] gives the following formulae for calculation of tensile $\sigma_{\tau\tau}$ and shear σ_{nr} stresses:

$$\sigma_{\tau\tau} = \frac{3}{2} \sigma_x \alpha , \quad \sigma_{nr} = \frac{3}{4} \sigma_x , \quad (14)$$

here σ_x is a parameter associated with the real load in the experiment, the beam width and the beam depth. We reduce the applied load to the variable σ_x with the dimension of stress for convenience. $\alpha = S/h$ is the span-to-depth ratio. Analyses in the literature operate with the tensile and shear stress. In reality, an experiment gives only the value associated with the load at the failure. Therefore, using data from [4] we will employ only the values recalculated back from the reported tensile and shear stresses to the reduced load σ_x .

Fig. 1 shows the dependence of the load parameter on the span-to-depth ratio α for the variety of angles φ_0 between fibre and the the load axis from 0 up to 45 degrees. Even keeping in mind the distinction in the simulated and experimental structures (the experiment [4] uses the fabric reinforced specimens, we calculate the unidirectional fibrous composite), the correlation is obvious.

The shear failure

Firstly we analyse the case of 'short beam' with $S/h = 3$. Figure 2 shows the failure picture that exactly corresponds to the presentation about the shear mode [7]. The detachment of the failure zone from the outer layers of the beam (opposite to the point of application of the load) is clear seen. The concentration of the stress at the point of loading is natural. Due to the

crosswise compression with respect to the fibre direction in the failure zone, the debonding zone is not coincident with the fracture zone. The influence of the clamping effect on the debonding zone at periphery of the beam is out of our interest in the present paper.

Fig. 2: The stress limit zones (a) and the possible debonding zone (the excess in the microstress - b) for the symmetrical loading; the span-to-depth ratio is 3.

In the case of the off-axis loading the picture is almost the same for the failure zones, but the zones, which are suspected to be debonded, have some overlapping of the zones in the vicinity of the applied load and over the outer surface of the beam (Fig. 3, $\varphi_0 = 30^\circ$, the angle is countered in the counterclockwise direction from the vertical axis directed downward).

Fig. 3: The stress limit zones (a) and the possible debonding zone (b) for the off-axis loading (the angle is 30 deg); the span-to-depth ratio is 3.

Thus, in the case of $\alpha = 3$ the shear fracture occurs in the studied range of the angles. For the cases considered the tensile stress is low both in the composite as a whole and in fibres along the fibre direction.

It should be noted that even in the case of low span-to-depth ratio some influence of the fibre direction on the failure zone is noticeable in the outer (tensile) region opposite to the point of the load application.

Mixed mode of failure

Fig. 4: The stress limit zones (a) and the possible debonding zone (b) for the symmetrical loading; the span-to-depth ratio is 5.

In the middle range of the span-to depth-ratio $S/h = 5$ for the symmetrical loadings ($\varphi_0 = 0^\circ$) the failure mode is still the shear one (Fig. 4). The widening of the tensile zone at the opposite surface to the load point becomes quite noticeable.

At $\varphi_0 = 30^\circ$ (Fig. 5) and more angles the mode can be considered to be changed to the mixed mode (in classification [7]). In the failure zone the debonding is quite probable.

Fig. 5: The stress limit zones (a) and the possible debonding zone (b) for the off-axis loading (the angle is 30 deg); the span-to-depth ratio is 5.

The tensile failure

At large span-to-depth ratios ($\alpha = 10$ and 20 in this subsection) the influence of tension on the failure is obvious in the variety of angles. At the same time, some peculiarities take place.

Fig. 6: The stress limit zones (a,d), the tensile stress limit zone (b), the possible debonding zone (c) for the symmetrical loading; the span-to-depth ratios are 10 (a,b,c) and 20 (d).

The case of symmetrical loading is drawn in Fig. 6, the failure starts on the opposite surface to the load point, the tensile stress and the debonding indicator are significant too. The appearance of the zones of localised deformation is seen especially clear at $S/h = 20$ (Fig. 6,d).

At these ratios the off-axis case is also characterised by the tensile failure. However, the features of the mixed failure mode are appeared, too. This is especially noticeable at the large off-axis angle (Fig. 7 a,b,c at $\varphi_0 = 45^\circ$).

Due to the specific fibre orientation in the given sample configurations, σ_f becomes significant at the large span-to-depth ratios and at the load with φ_0 more than 30° (in that part of the beam where orientation is in agreement with the load direction), the tensile stresses and the debonding zone are concentrated at the outer surface.

Fig. 7: The stress limit zones (a), the tensile failure zone (b), the possible debonding zone (c) and the fibre fracture zone (d) for the off-axis loading (the angle is 45 deg); the span-to-depth ratios are 10 (a,b,c) and 20(d).

CONCLUSION

The direct numerical simulation of the three-point bending test has shown that the load parameter correlates experiments quite adequately for the variety of the off-axis angles and span-to-depth ratios. At low span-to-depth ratios ($\alpha = 3$ for the given set of constituents) the shear failure mode is realised at the variety of the off-axis angles. However, even in the low range of span-to-depth ratios the influence of fibre orientation is essential. At $\alpha = 5$ the mixed failure mode takes place for the off-axis loading. At the large span-to-depth ratios ($\alpha = 10$ and 20 for the given composite) a steady tensile fracture takes place. Under these conditions, the fibre fracture is more probable at the off-axis test. At the symmetrical loading the areas of localised deformation are appeared clearly.

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